

HEROES OF THE SPANISH INDEPENDENT THEATRE:

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Under the forty-year regime of Francisco Franco, Spanish culture suffered much in all aspects and at all levels. Artistic and literary creation was extremely limited by censorship, to the point that many artists and writers “self-censored” in order to be able to publish and for fear of being imprisoned or expelled from the country. Fascism and nationalism flourished, and Spain found itself culturally empty, almost without any exchange with the rest of the world. People from the opposition to the Franco regime—writers, actors, workers, and other theater-makers who were censored by the Falange—sought means to continue their professions without losing their leftist ideology. More importantly, they sought non-commercial means, dedicated to the work, to dramatic art, and to contact with the Spanish people, specifically with non-bourgeois people. This search resulted in the formation of autonomous theatrical groups, the Independent Theatre, an important phenomenon not only for Spain, but as a new chapter in the history of world theatre.

We define the so-called “Teatro Independiente” in relation to what it was not: commercial theatre. Thus, it is necessary for us to understand the purpose and functioning of the established commercial theatre in the years preceding the independent emergence. We are concerned with the era after the civil war of 1936-1939 because with the fall of the Second Republic and the establishment of the Falange as the national government, a new stage in Spanish history begins...an obvious point for embarking on the study of any movement of the last forty years.

Spanish Commercial Theatre

One can read in any work about Spanish theatre that in the years after the war—the forties and fifties—the commercial theatre was lacking much. It was theatre for Spanish consumption only, and for an exclusively bourgeois audience. The entrepreneurs and writers knew what type of drama the bourgeoisie would enjoy, and they provided it, with no attempt to introduce new forms or to experiment with what they had. Francisco Ruiz Ramón points out some general trends of the post-war commercial theatre in his work, *Historia del Teatro Español: Siglo XX*:¹

1. The importance of the “well-made piece,” everything calculated and without surprises, with elegant and witty dialogue;
2. Of not attacking fundamentally or with violence certain grave fundamental problems, adopting... the elegant tone of a scandalous chronicle;
3. Of superficiality; it is a theatre for entertaining oneself and little more. It is not a critical theatre, but rather pleasant, witty, well-written, comic. There is no social criticism, or, at best, it can be a criticism of manners;
4. Many historical dramas; large stage spectacles and costumes, elaborations of the great history of Spain, celebrations of the country's heroes to affirm the feeling of national pride.

A well-known author of this era to whom many of these generalizations apply is **José María Pemán** (1898). Pemán wrote historical theatre in verse, thesis plays (right-wing propaganda), comedies of manners, *castiza* farces, and adaptations of classic theatre. “Pemán converts (*historical theatre in verse*) into a theatre of propaganda for certain traditional ideals, in which a simplistic or exemplary vision of history dominates, seen always from the outside and with a rhetorical gesture, not without a heavy sentimental load.”²

Post-war commercial theatre took no risks, facing a rigid censorship and a nationalist bourgeois public. In a way it was like the European romantic theatre of the 19th century, a theatre of loud laughter and tears, but of worse literary quality, as it did not produce works of universal value but rather superficial comedies to reassure an already reassured audience.

... the playwrights, skilled in their craft, have fulfilled toward their public the same function of censors, guides, or entertainers characteristic of the traditional playwright... without calling into question said function in the system of values on which it is founded.³

The need to create a theatre separate from bourgeois commercial theatre manifested even before the civil war in the so-called *casas del pueblo* (people’s houses”) of Barcelona. From 1931 until the war, the houses of the people functioned as part of the workers’ movement in Catalunya, which later represented an important faction among the Republican forces in the war. In the houses of the people—various small private halls in neighborhoods around Barcelona—worker groups met for assemblies and political performances. Clearly this “theatre” was very limited and only existed for a specific audience (worker and leftist), but in it we see the roots of future movements, of a critical and social theatre, with current importance still. There were also other halls, the *fomentos*, which mounted right-wing fascist theatre. In the *casas del pueblo* and the *fomentos* one can see some of the basic and important differences between the independent and the commercial theatre. They are: 1) the dichotomy between a worker audience and a bourgeois one, and of course, 2) the political distinction between the two, extremely important during the Franco regime. This is not to say that all commercial theatre operators were of the right, but rather that they took advantage of the popular and accepted form, which under Franco and censorship was discussed above.

The *casas del pueblo* continued to provide a site for those worker functions during the war, but under very difficult circumstances. They gave performances without lighting and set decorations, in any available site; everything theatrical was lacking, except the actors and the text. Among the authors of this “theatre of the rearguard” figure **García Lorca, Max Aub, Rafael Alberti, Miguel Hernández, Ramon Sender**, and other Spanish playwrights, poets and writers. As it was a theatre of propaganda, it did not concern itself much with dramatic aesthetics, neither in the writing nor in the performance. The important thing always had to be the socio-political message and the sense of unity created among the attendees.

Franco and Censors Take Over

At the end of the war, the Republicans saw themselves defeated by the Falange. Many people of the left fled the country or were killed. About 300,000 people were “disappeared”; many more fell silent and lived in a climate of suppression and fear. Catalunya was a region subjected, like the Basque Country, to the most ignominious arbitrariness: it lost its Statute of Autonomy, saw its mother tongue of Catalan prohibited in public; an infinity of cultural organisms were dissolved, such as the Institute

of Catalan Studies. Hundreds of thousands of books were destroyed for the sole fact of being written in Catalan.⁴

The *casas del pueblo* became either Catholic cooperatives under the church, or “regional houses” of dance, art, and theater like the *fomentos* — all Falangist. During the years immediately following the war, left-wing theater was basically nonexistent. When possible, small groups of the opposition gathered wherever they could, entirely clandestinely, for anti-Falangist demonstrations or performances. They announced the meetings very carefully among themselves the day it took place, and at the determined hour four or five cars arrived at a private home or hall to “stage” the piece — clearly without any elaboration. All of this could happen within two hours or less, and after the meeting they quickly left before the police arrived if they had been tipped off. Such clandestine gatherings also provided an opportunity to read or perform censored and unpublishable texts during the course of the Francoist government.

The imposition of censorship implied many changes in the artistic and cultural world of Spain, from the alienation of several important writers to changes in the nuances of literary and artistic styles that appeared over the last forty years. It was a rigid and at the same time arbitrary and unpredictable censorship, for which there was never an absolute definition of the matter of what deserved to be prohibited and what approved. The **Junta de Censura de Obras Teatrales** operated—God knows why—under the Ministry of Information and Tourism in Madrid. Only this central body could approve the presentation of a work, no matter where in all of Spain it was to take place.

The process was as follows: at an internal level, any group—professional, amateur, or university — that wanted to stage a performance had to send three copies of the text to said Junta in Madrid, with the name of the group or person responsible and the geographic area (Barcelona, Valencia, etc.) of performance, where it was read by a priest, a military officer, and some other Ministry official. Then there were three options: Approved, Approved with cuts, or Denied. But even approval of the text after this reading was not enough to present the work. If approved, the Junta sent the group a “blue card” without which they could do nothing. With the card they could rehearse, build sets and costumes, etc., but one or two days before opening night another censor came for the “viewing of the general rehearsal.” This person could prohibit the work if the company did not follow the cuts in the text, or if something “of a prohibitive character” appeared in the performance. Many times, after spending a great deal on preparations, securing a venue, and rehearsing, the night before opening the censor would come and decide to prohibit it. Those who were bolder and perhaps somewhat more clever would put on a “special” performance for the censor—everything very acceptable—and the following night they would change everything, including the sets and the lines of the text, and stage the work as they wanted. Of course it was a fairly grave risk, and sometimes it ended with the suspension of the show and some members of the group in jail, as happened with **Els Joglars**, a Catalan group, with the production *La torna* in 1977.

Another aspect of censorship had to do with the work-audience relationship, with respect to geography. After obtaining the blue card, the group or producer had to take it to the Civil Government of the area and request permission to open in a specific venue and during a fixed season. If the governor of the area in question believed the work represented a threat to the ideology or security of the Civil Government, he could prohibit it in that area, or on certain dates. It was a censorship of “time and space,” because, for example, if there was a strike or planned demonstration on a day during the run of a “questionable” work, the Civil Government would prohibit the opening on that day. It

was so arbitrary that a work could open in one city and not another, or even in one venue and not another — all at the governor’s discretion.

As if all this were not ridiculous enough, there was also the *Ley de Locales* (venue law), applicable to all performance venues. The *Ley de Locales* was composed of numerous regulations and specifications for the venue (emergency exits, door regulations, space limitations, etc.), with all of which no theater in all of Spain could comply! So, if a reason was needed to stop the performance of a work, the authorities could close the theater for not complying with the *Ley de Locales*. Theater people called it the “law of fear” because there was always the possibility that police might come to inspect the venue for any reason.

Under such rigid censorship it is very easy to understand the frustration and anger experienced by many modern Spanish writers. Since they could not publish or even hope to stage a minimally critical work against the Francoist system, they had three alternatives: 1) exile themselves and publish in other countries; 2) stay, write, and not publish; 3) “self-censor” their works in order to pass censorship. Of course, many authors like **Pemán**, **Victor Ruiz de Iriarte**, and **Edgar Neville**, to name a few, had no problem publishing or opening shows, since they did not criticize the system. But in writing with the intention of publishing, the Spanish author automatically “self-censored” — that is, committed to the accepted norm, converting or removing anything that could have been misinterpreted by the censor. An important author who avoided censorship in this way is **Antonio Buero Vallejo**. Vallejo, who was a communist during the civil war, wrote throughout the forties, fifties, and sixties a “conservative-reformist” drama, superficially critical and elusive with respect to censorship. He knew well how the censorship functioned and always stayed within the limitations while introducing a more realistic drama of socio-political interest to the Spanish stage.

While Buero Vallejo was writing, Falangist theater flourished in various forms. First of all, the **National Theaters** provided the most commercial and influential stage for popular authors like Pemán and Miguel Mihura. There was also a repertory theater composed of commercial companies that traveled through Spain in cars or trains to present works in various cities. They did tours of four or five days, changing the work at each opening. These repertory groups were extensions of the National Theater and followed the fascist theater model of bourgeois ideology.

Another proponent of Falangist theater was the Teatro Español Universitario (TEU). Under Franco there was one political party (the Falange), one vertical workers’ union, and one student union: the Sindicato Español Universitario (SEU).

This single organization directed and controlled all student activities in all areas: theater, culture, information, scholarships, labor management, social assistance, etc.; membership was mandatory and automatic for students.¹

Non-Falangist students had no outlet for vocal or literary expression. Censorship, lack of training, shortage of teachers and information impeded theatrical activity, and of course the Sindicato would not allow it. There was only one school dedicated to theater that was not Falangist: the **Escola Adria Gual** of Barcelona. There the Catalan theater movement was consolidated, but not until the 1960’s.

¹ Indeed, when this paper was written, in 1980, the student body at the University of Barcelona were on strike for autonomy from state control. Things were still just starting to change after Franco’s death in 1976.

From the TEU emerged important authors and writers like **Alfonso Sastre**, **José María de Quinto**, and **Alfonso Paso**. These were rebels, dissatisfied with Spanish society and they wanted to bring a radical and reformist stance to the public through publications and theatre. With his social concern, Sastre was the leader of two theatrical movements that positioned themselves against the conservative commercial theatre. In *Prólogo Patético* (1950-1953), Sastre summarizes his ideas on the political and social function of theatre, and in 1950 he announced the foundation of the **Social Agitation Theatre** (T.A.S.) whose ideology consisted of “theatre as an instrument of agitation and transformation of society.” “*This new step, apparently useless, is, however, the first practical awakening of consciousness of the new Spanish youth.*”⁷

But the T.A.S. did not go beyond manifesto and ideology. Sastre continued forming his ideas about the capability of theatre to influence and change society and in 1960 he founded, with J.M. de Quinto, the **Realistic Theatre Group** (G.T.R.). In many articles and several books from 1955-1970⁸, he developed his ideas on the role of theatre in modern society, accentuating the need for what he called an “emergency theatre.” In *Anatomy of Realism* he writes:

Social-realism points to the great themes of a time in which the social has been erected as the supreme category of human concern. They are: “freedom, responsibility, guilt, repentance, and salvation.” But captured not “in the human person as an individual,” but “in the human person as a relationship, as forming part of social order or chaos.”⁹

The 60s Brings Change

It seems to me a very important fact that Sastre and the G.T.R. managed to mount three works between January and March of 1961, establishing contact with an attentive public, and proposing a dialogue on social matters never touched in popular Spanish theatre. These performances signaled the arrival of a decade of vital internal change for all of Spain.

We have seen that throughout the 40s and 50s almost all of the theatre in Spain was Falangist, composed of the commercial, the TEU, and amateur or repertory groups. During the 60s, the opposition to fascist theatre increased greatly and groups began to work and fight for their right to premiere new dramas by liberal and progressive writers. They were years of change for Spain on all fronts, a time in which it opened up more to the Western world, to economic relations and to investment in the country. People enjoyed the advent of television and tourism brought money and new culture to a people that had been almost isolated from the rest of the world for twenty years.

Two specific phenomena that helped promote the new theatrical activity were: 1) the beginning of strikes and demonstrations by the opposition to Francoism, and 2) the emigration or exile of authors to France, which resulted in a new circuit around Toulouse for the newly formed groups and collectives. Since they could not go to established commercial theaters, these contrary groups took advantage of the activities of students, workers, and other militants of the opposition to the Regime—communists, anarchists, socialists, etc.—illegal groups that gathered in neighborhoods, in factories, and in towns for demonstrations. This created a support infrastructure for the nascent Teatro Independiente.

Authors and theatre people who left Spain to escape the censorship and the fascist government established themselves throughout Europe, and Toulouse became once again a center of cultural

activity starting in the 50s. For Spanish authors like **Fernando Arrabal**, who lived and wrote in France starting in 1954, the new country offered a liberal and progressive climate in which vital literature of high aesthetic quality and world renown thrived. The self-exile of authors like Arrabal, Sastre, and Alberti certainly was a loss for Spain, but it was an important gain for the literary world and something they simply had to do, faced with the alternative of staying under a an insensitive and senseless government.

The authors of the so-called “new Spanish theatre”—contemporary drama that starts at the end of the 50s—took dramatic trends established by French authors like Beckett, Genet, and Ionesco and applied them to Spanish themes. But since many of the new authors wrote political dramas critical of the Spanish government, they had a hard time escaping censorship. As a result, they either decided to write what they wanted and just not publish in Spain, or they wrote with no intention of publishing at all.

Contemporary Spanish drama has been divided into two main categories: lighthearted comic comedy of the Broadway-West End Boulevard variety, and that of political allegory. Under this system, only these two types of drama are possible. The former is designed to entertain the audience while avoiding all matters in dispute. The second attempts to criticize indirectly, partly for artistic reasons and partly because of a desire to pass the censor, if possible. (“Subtle intellect,” as Shaw said in years past, “is never a great strength of the censor”).¹⁰

Sometimes unpublishable pieces appeared on foreign stages, such as *El hombre y la mosca* by José Ruibal, which premiered at the State University of New York in Binghamton, N.Y. in 1972. They were also presented clandestinely to small audiences in private locations, and in public under the *cámara y ensayo* (“camera and rehearsal”) law. This new legislation (from around 1960) allowed the presentation of an “acceptable” work in any location for **one to three days**, no more. The authorities believed there was no danger in allowing a show with a maximum of three performances and were thus able to give a little ground to the opposition. They also relaxed censorship somewhat for *cámara y ensayo* premieres, so school and independent groups took advantage of the opportunity to make three presentations of works they could not otherwise stage.

An important element that helped popularize and support new progressive works was the introduction of theater journals such as *Primer Acto* (1957), *Yorick* (1960), and *Piripijaina* (1974). In *Primer Acto* and *Piripijaina* there always appeared new, generally progressive pieces of leftist affinity (both have ceased publication). For the burgeoning leftist theatre world, *Primer Acto* played the role of an enthusiastic father nurturing a child just learning to walk. These journals treated the independent groups with respect and little criticism, because they were doing something difficult and brave in forging a new Spanish theater and a new dramatic aesthetic.

Intrinsic factors that affected the aesthetics of the coming Teatro Independiente were: 1) the type of drama produced, and 2) the economic situation of the groups. As for the selection of works, they generally followed these points:

- a) rejection of naturalism (which had been almost the sole dramatic form produced in Spain for years);
- b) sympathy for rebellious, anti-establishment authors;
- c) tendency toward farce and the Commedia dell’Arte style;
- d) use of song (another departure from naturalism).

Censorship necessitated this departure from realism on the part of authors who wanted to criticize the system. It resulted in very intricate situations and an extremely strange level of communication between characters, resembling the French *Theater of the Absurd*. They wrote symbolism and surrealism, exemplified by **José Ruibal** and **Fernando Arrabal**. They created situations in which gestures speak, since it is much harder to censor dramatic movements than written texts. So, in its early stages the T.I. did not represent much literary validity, but rather more leftist ideology or simple entertainment. A representative of independent troupe **los Goliardos** stated, "*What matters is to be concrete with respect to a problem using a common language representative of a certain community...*,"¹¹ as the *casas del pueblo* did before the war; but in public, under censorship, it was nearly impossible.

The economic situation of the T.I. from the beginning was grim. Since theater groups were formed without recognition or help from anyone, they were self-managing and egalitarian in the division of money. They could not afford the luxury of large stage productions and costumes, especially when they carried everything necessary in a few cars or a small truck. Nor could they spend money on cleaning and caring for expensive costumes or ornate decorations. So, they were immediately very limited aesthetically and had to make use of new or unusual staging methods. The need to use little space, to work in unknown and poorly adaptable locations, to lighten their load and move frequently gave rise to new types of staging, scenery, technical apparatus, etc.

Another implied limitation concerns the use of actors. In small groups (generally made up of 8 to 12 members), actors often had to play multiple roles, which also produced a comic effect. They reintroduced an element of ancient Greek theater—the use of masks to differentiate between characters, as the itinerant *Commedia dell'Arte* groups had done in the past. Again, it must be remembered that the text and the message were what mattered most, and less the manner of presentation. All of this suggests a theater of poor aesthetic quality compared to the more luxurious established theaters, but also of youthful vitality and ingenuity.

So it was after twenty years of dictatorship, under a censorship so rigid as to be absurd, and in the midst of some of the most crucial social changes for Spain in all its history, that a new theatrical phenomenon was born. It involved the organization and professionalization of already existing itinerant groups, and moreover of intellectuals, students, and unemployed theater people, all in opposition to the establishment. The newly formed groups were self-managing and completely independent of any venue or producer (of course, given that all venues were commercial and Falangist), and therefore also independent of the demands of the bourgeois audience that attended established theater. This, finally, is what we call the *Teatro Independiente*, and henceforth, the **T.I.** And it was in 1964 that the first true independent professional theatre group was formed, **los Goliardos**—a fact that marks the introduction of a new stage in the history of Spanish theatre: "*...the birth of los Goliardos responds to a general awakening of consciousness that, starting from the European avant-garde, is directed toward the small sectors of the country.*"¹²

During the sixties and seventies, a long battle took place between the T.I. and commercial theater, and the latter found itself in crisis. It was no longer a popular theater, but a boring pastime for the bourgeoisie. Never any risks, never any disagreement as to the church, the military, or the dictatorship, and always of mediocre theatrical quality. What increased the rupture between the independent and commercial interests was the selection of works by both sides, and their interpretations. Producers and directors of the national theaters wanted to copy the great famous European theaters, so they took popular well-known texts and staged them, altered to appear right-wing or Fascist, in support of the administration's ideology. One example is Brecht's *Threepenny Opera*. From the outside it seemed

the administration was opening itself a little to the artistic world by allowing the presentation of this liberal text, but in reality they continued the promotion of Fascist theater. But two could play this game. The leftists did a great deal to counter the establishment, including adapting right-wing texts to avoid censorship without problems, and in production changing them to be leftist, in support of their causes.

The public welcomed the freshness and variety offered by the independent groups, and dramatic art began to reach towns and audiences that had never experienced the magic of theater before. In 1969, five years after the formation of **los Goliardos**, the **Teatro Capsa** opened in Barcelona, the first venue that dared to stage progressive works.

Following the model of the Goliardos, other groups formed and created tours around Madrid and Barcelona, and toward Toulouse. Names began to become known: grupo Tábano (Madrid), Els Joglars, Els Comediants (the two Catalan ones), Dagoll-Dagom, etc. — each year more troupes and more pieces sent to the Censorship Board in Madrid. In 1971, the **T.E.I.** (*Pequeño Teatro de Magallanes*) appeared, and in 1973, the first stable independent theater, the **Sala Villarroel** in Barcelona. Others soon followed: the **Cadarso** in Madrid (formed by the group *Tábano*); **Quart 23** in Valencia (*Teatro Club Universitario* and *Studio Teatro*); and the **Teatro Lliure** in Barcelona, ... some with resident companies, others that only provided a venue for touring groups, but all in opposition to the Falange.

The administration did everything possible to interfere with functioning of these independent groups, including the application of the *Ley de Locales* and the censorship of several plays for almost no reason. Notable examples include *El retablo del flautista* by Teixedor and *Castañuelas 70* by *Tábano*, which was authorized by the censors in 1970 but subsequently banned “throughout the entire national territory” by the Ministry of the Interior.

Another instance of official interference was the closure of the **Sala Cadarso** in Madrid in 1977, just as it was about to premiere Gorky's *The Mother*.

In any case, the dilemma offered little hope: either close the venue or accept the oversight of the Advisory Board, which effectively meant subjecting the venue to a Law of Premises riddled with ambiguities, anachronisms, and traps.¹⁴

The aforementioned *Ley de Locales* was one of the most controversial and outrageous weapons instigated by the administration, and it was the subject of many complaints from the affected groups. A report on the situation of the T.I. notes:

A privileged instrument of the oligopoly and of the Administration is the current *Ley de Locales*, regarding which it is sufficient to point out: 1. That it is an anachronistic legal framework which does not stand up to comparison with the legislation of other countries; 2 That its application is arbitrary, since 100 percent of authorized theaters would be in violation of it if it were strictly enforced...¹⁵

It goes without saying that the theater people of the opposition approached their profession as combatants in a war, because during the dictatorship of Franco it truly was a battle. It got to the point that in 1976, during the opening of a piece by Alfonso Sastre, a bomb exploded at the Sala Villarroel, an attack by the “Triple A”—the *Alianza Apostólica Anticomunista de España*.¹⁶

At the reading level, three pieces representative of the Teatro Independiente stand out and deserve mention: *Castañuelas 70* (1970), by grupo **Tábano**; *El retablo del flautista*, by **Jordi Teixedor**; and

Antaviana, by grupo **Dagoll-Dagom**. *Antaviana*, based on stories by Pere Calders, premiered at the Sala Villarroel of Barcelona in 1978, and afterwards had productions in Valencia, Balearic Islands, Madrid, Alicante, Vitoria, a long tour of Cataluña, and returned for another session at the Villarroel. In the end, it was one of the greatest successes of the T.I.

It is important to note that at the beginning of the 1970s, 90% of Spanish theater was commercial, and by the end of the decade, nearly 80% was independent. To expand the activities of independent groups and improve communication between them, proponents of the T.I. organized a great number of festivals and assemblies throughout Spain, beginning with the *I Festival de Vitoria* in 1975. These occasions provided opportunities and venues for conferences of the newly formed *Asamblea de Teatro Independiente Profesional* (A.T.I.P.). In meetings during the festivals, they discussed the problems and activities of the T.I., and invited groups gave performances—many times of works in their own languages: Basque, Catalan, Galician, etc. An important festival was the *II Semana de Teatro de Cuenca*, in March 1976. It was organized by the association of *Amigos de Teatro*, under the patronage of the Caja Provincial de Ahorros de Cuenca. Suddenly, in a fairly small town with no living theater, six performances were staged by five independent groups, each opening packed to the brim with people from the town and surrounding areas. The press began to introduce the ideology and the problems of the T.I. to the public in magazines and newspapers, and the festivals attracted much attention as they were progressive and controversial cultural occurrences with respect to the administration. In an article about the *II Semana en Cuenca*, Felin Petite, director of the group **La Farandula**, was interviewed. He said, “...the national problem is political at this moment one hundred percent, and a theater that has been characterized by its criticism cannot remain on the margins of this current,” and about the General Theater Law, “...this type of activity (the T.I.) is not registered nor encompassed in any concrete provision of the law, because at the level of Theaters of Cámara y Ensayo by which it is governed, the definition is completely false.” Thus, the grievances of the T.I. were made public, and in many documents and manifestos the A.T.I.P. made its demands to the administration known. Generally, the response was null. We will discuss some of the proposals and solutions put forward by the A.T.I.P. below.

The history continues: in 1976 Franco died, and with him, the Sindicato Vertical. Official censorship continued until 1978. In Cataluña a new assembly was created, the *Teatro de Grec*, but within it political forces arose—anarchists, socialists, bourgeois—and in the end the professionals broke apart with many ideas and nothing unified. In 1977 the A.T.I.P. died for similar reasons, and what remained of the lost unification were theater centers or zones, with ever more stable theaters instead of itinerant ones. Since the Ministry of Tourism and Culture (M.I.T.) would only give money to stable centers, itinerant groups began to establish themselves: one each in Seville, Valencia, Bilbao, and Zaragoza, and two in Madrid and Barcelona. These were called *teatros de zonas*. As of 1980, there are 10-12 venues in Spain that work only with Independent Theater; in 1972 there were none.

Another recent phenomenon that deserves mention is that of the so-called "cooperatives" or collectives, which to me seem like simply another name for independent groups. However, it is worth citing some of the characteristics applicable to a collective and, I believe, to the majority of independent groups as well:

1. The theater cooperative is a form of self-management that provides work for many actors who frequently find themselves unemployed.
2. Democratic internal organization; it requires the participation of all its members in resolving problems posed by the creation and performance of a show.

3. Continuity is the primary and principal objective of the cooperative; continuity on several levels: a)
 - a. continuity of the name;
 - b. continuity of members;
 - c. continuity of style or theatrical practice;
 - d. continuity of the generation of new cooperatives, in a process of multiplication.
4. The cooperative aims to maintain relations with the professional theater world and to involve itself in political, professional, and labor matters, as well as to encourage cooperative experiences within commercial theater.
5. The greatest difference between a cooperative and any independent group is that cooperatives are generally composed of people from professional theater—that is to say, they already have professional experience and are looking for another outlet for their talents.
6. Objectives, also applicable to Independent Theatre:
 - a. self-financing;
 - b. seeking and obtaining their own venues;
 - c. seeking and creating new non-bourgeois audiences;
 - d. self-criticism and artistic standards;
 - e. establishing themselves as a cooperative as a legal framework (when contracting with managers).¹⁸

In telling the history of this theatrical/social movement I have touched on some of the many problems of the Independent Theater. These are problems discussed countless times in innumerable conferences, attacked by the press and analyzed in many articles; acceptable solutions are almost never reached by all parties. Since there are so many matters and nuances to the problems of the T.I., it suffices here to point out just some of the most profound questions that affect or have affected the cultural activity of the T.I.

Since 1976 some of the most difficult problems for the groups have actually disappeared, such as that of the *Sindicato Vertical de Espectáculos* and that of censorship. I have already discussed the functioning and effect of censorship; I now want to briefly describe that of the *Sindicato*—a complicated matter that is itself the subject of many studies and debates. Just as the *Sindicato Español Universitario* directed all student activity, there was only one official body in control of all types of performances: the *Sindicato del Espectáculo*. This “theatrical union,” if you will, imposed that each venue comply with various requirements (number of employees, cards, regular taxes, etc.) with which a majority of self-managing groups could not comply. The *Sindicato del Espectáculo* was contained in the Labor Ordinance of Artists but was not included in anything concerning independent groups. New venues and new groups could not obtain help from the *Sindicato* or the Ministry—the only sources of official legislation for theatrical activities—simply for being proponents of this “insurgent” movement. “*The greatest problem for the theater group is the lack of legal entity, the total non-recognition of its professionalism.*”²⁰ The intrinsic connection between culture and politics—and where power resided—became all too clear.

A contradictory aspect of this legal problem is that the *Sindicato* provided the only form of unification for state theater, and when it disappeared in 1976, new measures were needed to ensure professional solidarity. On January 31, 1976, a dinner was held at a restaurant in Getafe, attended by 800 professionals from various sectors of Art and Culture: cinema, theater, R.T.V.E., writers, plastic artists, etc., where two important documents were made public, and proposals from various Art and Culture Committees present were shared. In **Appendix I** you will find the *Program of the Junta Democrática de Teatro de Madrid Región*, which was presented at the dinner. Three months later, on April 29, 1976, the provisional commission of the *Federación de Grupos de Teatro Independiente* presented to the M.I.T. (*Dirección General de Teatro*) another similar report on the current situation of the T.I. Many of the points

coincided, especially regarding the opening of venues, abolition of censorship, decentralization of theater, and amnesty for those exiled or repressed for political and union reasons.

The issue of theater decentralization is one that continues as a source of discussion today, which I want to outline here. Decentralization can be defined as:

... the dissemination of scenic activity across the entire surface of the country, giving rise to the birth of permanent theatrical hubs in different geographical areas, according to the economic, demographic, and cultural conditions of the regions.²¹

This had been the desire and the task of the itinerant groups since the beginning of the movement: to bring theater and culture to the masses and in the language of the multiple regions of Spain. Decentralization also appears as a prominent subject in almost all the documents and manifestos of the T.I., a point of accusation:

... [it] starts from the verification of the existence of an authentic cultural discrimination for the majority of Spaniards, based on two fundamental points:

- a) Classism: In that theatrical activity is oriented toward the satisfaction of the cultural needs of the upper layers of the bourgeoisie. Hence the choice of themes and the pricing policy.
- b) Centralism: In that the distribution of shows is limited almost exclusively to Madrid and Barcelona.²²

Independent and self-managed groups had tried to establish theater in towns throughout Spain, and to establish decentralized bases, but as Juan Hormigón informs us in *Theater, Realism, and Mass Culture*:

The material base (building, equipment, scenic, technical and lighting, mobilizable capital, etc.) can never come from private investment if one wants to free the theater from its abusive surplus value, [its] character as a commodity and convert it into a public cultural service available to the masses. ... (as) they have created and maintain the infrastructure of stable European theaters (all of them decentralized).²³

In other words, economic subsidy from the government and other organizations is needed,²⁴ and for that we return to the need for effective legislation 1) to recognize the value of culture and dramatic art, and 2) to legally place theatrical production in a framework of guarantees, incentives, and free from interferences, *"from the narrow definition of what 'legally' is a theatrical building, to the absurd nature of the actor's card."*²⁵

All these demands and needs of the T.I. reflect the needs of a free democratic society; they are *"claims that, in order to become a reality, touch the socio-political-economic structure of the theater; a structure that is also linked to the general [structure] of the State apparatus."*²⁶ This intrinsic and universal quality of theater - which reflects the society and culture in which it takes place, and this crucial relationship determines where the theater can function, for whom it exists, the material presented, ... all aspects of theatrical production.

A new concern among members of the T.I., and for which it has been criticized, is the lack of representation of works written by Spanish authors. In a survey with some of the prominent current authors,²⁷ *Piripijaina* asked them, *"What would have to change in the theater infrastructure, as it is produced in our country, so that the premiere of the new theater would be possible?"* From the various responses we can gain an understanding of the attitudes of the "victims" of the system. José Velasco cited some reasons why

many new authors do not premiere: “a) *mental laziness, or the preference for known and safe texts; b) Pure snobbery in many cases, and c) the disregard for the function of the literary text as an element of the theatrical show...*”²⁸ something that is influenced in large part by the audience. The majority of the Spanish people have not learned, nor attempted to learn, how to read a play or interpret a performance. Symbols and metaphors are evasive, and as we have seen, the type of drama that has been produced in Spain in the last twenty years (1960-1980), which new authors usually write, is usually based on vague comparisons and complicated symbols. Velasco continues, “*In any case, there could be no new theater if a new audience did not previously exist.*”²⁹

Angel García Pintado responded, “*It would have to come ... a freedom to open venues without great legal requirements. That is, abolition of the law on public venues.*” He also cites the need for “*official protection for those groups and entrepreneurs who stage theater by Spanish authors,*” and, “*logically this type of theater must be subsidized by the bourgeois power.*”³⁰ Pintada also speaks of the importance of creating professional theatrical training schools but does not discuss the union situation which seems to me to be possibly the most significant matter regarding the future in Spain of any theater profession.

Jerónimo Mozo commented on the subject of the modernization and vitality of Spanish theater:

...if the stagings do not take into account current dramatic trends; if the actors, in practice, ignore the latest acting techniques; we cannot say that we are premiering [new works], but in many cases, provoking logical failures.³¹

It is obvious, after reading the responses to this survey, that some deep and difficult changes are still necessary for the true renewal of Spanish theater. The authors and proponents of theater do not want to return to a preceding popular form, but rather to discover new directions and valid and representative themes of the current Spanish experience. They need to recapture the force with which they began and fought, the dedication that characterized those who worked to create and popularize the Independent Theater during the reign of Franco and fascism. They have gained much, and the prize is the ability to continue changing, growing, and creating.

NOTES

1. Francisco Ruiz Ramón, *History of Spanish Theater: 20th Century* (Cátedra, Madrid, 1977), p. 331.
2. *Ibid.*, p. 335.
3. *Ibid.*, p. 332.
4. Eduardo Pons Prades, "Catalonia in the Civil War," *Tiempo de historia*, Year VI, no. 62; January, 1980, p. 108.
5. Juan Antonio Hormigón, *Theater, Realism and Mass Culture* (Madrid: Edicusa, 1974), p. 101.
6. Ramón, p. 386.
7. Hormigón, p. 102.
8. Ramón, p. 387. Sastre's articles include: "Colloquies on Current Problems of Theater in Spain" (Santander, 1955); *Drama and Society* (Madrid: Taurus, 1956); "Art as Construction" (*Acento Cultural*, 1958); "Document on Spanish Theater" (1961); *Anatomy of Realism* (Barcelona: Seix Barral, 1965); and *The Revolution and the Critique of Culture* (Barcelona: Gribaldo, 1970).
9. *Ibid.*, p. 388.
10. Michael Benedikt and George Wellworth, eds., *Modern Spanish Theater* (E.P. Dutton & Co., Inc., 1969), p. 330. Translated by the author.
11. "Goliardos, or the Disintegration of a Group," *Primer Acto* no. 162; Nov., 1973, p. 58.
12. "Goliardos," *Primer Acto* no. 162; p. 59.
13. "Report produced by the provisional commission of the Federation of Independent Theater Groups," *Pipirijaina* no. 1; 1976, p. 9.
14. *Pipirijaina* no. 4; pp. 14–15.
15. "Document Three," *Pipirijaina* no. 1; 1976, p. 8.
16. *Pipirijaina* no. 4; p. 4.
17. *Norte Expres*, April 2, 1976, p. 32.
18. "Report of the Second Theater Week in Cuenca," March, 1976.
19. It should be noted here that, due to a lack of time and up-to-date information, it is certain that the current situation as of 1980. has changed from what I am able to describe.
20. "Report: Second Theater Week in Cuenca," April, 1976.
21. Hormigón, p. 17.
22. "Report on the Current Situation of Independent Theater," by the Federation of Independent Theater Groups, presented to the Ministry of Tourism and Culture, April 29, 1976.
23. Hormigón, p. 22.
24. A proposal on this matter can be found in Hormigón's *Theater, Realism and Mass Culture*.
25. Hormigón, p. 23.
26. "The Profession, CCOO and Trade Union Unity," *Pipirijaina* no. 4, p. 51.
27. *Pipirijaina* no. 6; January–February, 1978, p. 49.
28. *Ibid.*, p. 49.
29. *Ibid.*, p. 49.
30. *Ibid.*, p. 50.
31. *Ibid.*, p. 51.

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APPENDIX I

PROGRAM OF THE DEMOCRATIC JUNTA OF THEATRE OF MADRID-REGION

1. ABOLITION OF ALL TYPES OF CENSURE.
2. DEMOCRATIZATION OF ALL THE LEGISLATIVE AND EXECUTIVE ORGANS DETERMINATIVE IN THE SECTOR.
 - o a) Said organs will have to be composed of professionals chosen democratically.
3. DECENTRALIZATION OF THE THEATRICAL ACTIVITIES AND INFRASTRUCTURE.
4. FREEDOM OF ASSOCIATION AND UNIONIZATION.
5. SOCIAL SECURITY:
 - o a) Creation of subsidized cooperatives managed by the professionals.
 - o b) Dignified and effective Unemployment Insurance.
 - o c) Opening of new venues. Derogation of the current archaic legislation and creation of a new one that allows the utilization of new venues, which would represent new jobs in the face of the enormous unemployment that our profession suffers, accelerating the democratization of our sector, connecting it with a new public (neighborhoods, towns, etc.) until today marginalized from culture.
6. SCHOOLS AND TEACHING:
 - o a) New concept of professional formation.
 - o b) State subsidies to possible private schools.
 - o c) Rational preparation of the actor.
 - o d) Intervention of the students in the study plans.
 - o e) Dramatic creativity in children's education.
7. MISSION OF A DEMOCRATIC GOVERNMENT in the theatrical sector:
 - o a) New concepts of a National Theatre.
 - o b) Protection, aid and coordination of the exchange of theatrical activities throughout all the territory of the Spanish State.
8. GENERAL AMNESTY and return of the exiles that reaches all Spaniards without restrictions and therefore, all theatre professionals.

FOR A PROVISIONAL DEMOCRATIC GOVERNMENT AND WITHOUT EXCLUSIONS that guarantees real and effectively the putting into motion of these points.

Document of the Democratic Junta of Theatre of Madrid-Region presented publicly in the mentioned dinner of Getafe on the date January 31, 1976.
